

Figure 6c: The 10x10 vāstu for a fortress with a watchtower
(koṭṭāṭṭālakasaṃyuta), PI 8.212-226.

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|----------------|---------------|----------------|
| 1 Brahmā | 19 Satya | 37 Roga |
| 2 Marīcaka | 20 Bhṛṣa | 38 Vāyu |
| 3 Vivasvant | 21 Antarikṣa | 39 Nāga |
| 4 Mitra | 22 Agni | 40 Mukhya |
| 5 Pṛthivīdhara | 23 Pūṣan | 41 Bhallāṭa |
| 6 Āpa | 24 Vitatha | 42 Soma |
| 7 Āpavatsa | 25 Gṛhākṣata | 43 Ṛgi |
| 8 Savitr | 26 Yama | 44 Aditi |
| 9 Sāvitrī | 27 Gandharva | 45 Diti |
| 10 Indra | 28 Bhṛṅga | 46 Skanda |
| 11 Indrajit | 29 Mṛga | 47 Aryaman |
| 12 Rudra | 30 Pitṛ | 48 Jambha |
| 13 Rudradāsa | 31 Dauvārika | 49 Pilipiccha |
| 14 Īsa | 32 Sugrīva | 50 Carakī |
| 15 Parjanya | 33 Puṣpadanta | 51 Vidārī |
| 16 Jaya | 34 Pracetas | 52 Pūtanā |
| 17 Mahendra | 35 Asura | 53 Pāparākṣasī |
| 18 Sūrya | 36 Śoṣa | |

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53	49	39	40	41	42	43			50 46
37	38					44	45	14	
36		13		5		7		15	
35		12				6		16	
34				1				17	18
33		4				2		19	
32		10		3		9		20	
31		11				8		21	
48	30						23	22	
52	29	28	27	26	25	24			47 51

cells removed

